

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

APPLICATION OF BLOCKCHAIN IN IT INFRASTRUCTURE MANAGEMENT: NEW OPPORTUNITIES FOR SECURITY ASSURANCE

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Abstract

This article explores the application of blockchain technologies (BT) in managing IT infrastructure projects with the aim of enhancing security levels. It examines the potential of blockchain to ensure data protection, access control, and process automation through decentralized structures and immutable records. It is noted that the use of smart contracts and cryptographic methods can minimize the risks of cyberattacks and data leaks, while ensuring transparency and network resilience. The successful integration of blockchain solutions to optimize processes and improve IT system security is demonstrated through examples from companies like IBM, Walmart, and JP Morgan. The article discusses the advantages and challenges of implementing blockchain in existing systems, highlighting the necessity of a comprehensive approach and strategic planning for successful integration.

Keywords: blockchain, IT infrastructure, security, decentralization, smart contracts, data protection, automation.

Introduction

In the context of the rapid development of information technology and the increase in data volumes, the project IT infrastructure management is becoming an increasingly complex and vulnerable task. Traditional methods of ensuring the security of IT systems face challenges such as cyberattacks, data breaches, and integrity violations. In such circumstances, the search for new, more reliable solutions to protect and manage IT infrastructure becomes an urgent task. One of the promising approaches is the use of blockchain technology.

Blockchain is a decentralized and distributed data ledger system that ensures their indisputability, transparency and protection from unauthorized access. It was originally developed for financial transactions. Blockchain is currently being used in various fields, including logistics, healthcare, and digital asset management.

The purpose of this article is to analyze the possibilities of using blockchain technologies (BT) in managing the IT infrastructure of projects in order to increase the level of security. The article discusses how blockchain can help solve current security problems, what advantages and problems are associated with its implementation, as well as how this technology can transform existing approaches to IT resource management.

Main part. Principles of operation and advantages of blockchain technology

Blockchain is a distributed data storage system in which information is stored in a chain of blocks connected to each other using cryptographic methods [1]. Each block contains a unique timestamp and a reference to the previous block, ensuring the continuity and integrity of the entire chain (pic. 1).

Pic. 1. The scheme of operation of the blockchain technology

One of the main characteristics of the blockchain is **decentralization**. In traditional systems, data is controlled by a central server, which creates a «point of failure» and vulnerability to attacks. In the blockchain

system, all nodes of the network are equal and distributed according to different geolocation. This structure not only enhances security by eliminating single points of failure but also increases transparency (pic. 2).

Pic. 2. Decentralization of blockchain technology

Every change, such as a new transaction or block creation, must be confirmed by a majority of network participants. This makes the blockchain more resilient to failures and hacks, because an attacker will need to attack most nodes at the same time. This is practically impossible on the scale of global networks [2]. The decentralization of the blockchain has an impact on the **management of configurations** and updates of IT systems. Blockchain allows you to store data in a distributed network, where all changes are recorded and verified by participants. This ensures that each developer sees only the actual information and can verify its authenticity.

According to Statista, the cost of blockchain solutions in 2024 will be \$19 billion compared to \$6.6 billion in 2021 [3]. This confirms the growing interest in BT as a way to manage data that helps companies minimize the risks of changing or destroying it.

Another principle is **transparency and immutability**. All transactions are recorded in a block and be-

come part of a chain that is immutable and secured using cryptographic algorithms. This is especially important for banking and financial organizations. According to a Deloitte report, back in 2018, 68% of banks around the world believed that they would lose their competitive advantage if they did not implement blockchain technology [4].

The blockchain can be used to manage software updates. This ensures that each new version goes through the verification process and is distributed over the network in a secure way. This minimizes the risks associated with attacks during the upgrade phase and prevents the spread of vulnerable versions.

The blockchain works on the basis of **consensus**, that is, the general agreement of all network participants, according to which transactions are considered valid. This makes it possible to carry out decentralized confirmation of transactions and maintain the reliability of the system without the participation of a central authority (pic. 3).

Pic. 3. Blockchain consensus scheme

Common consensus mechanisms are Proof of Work (PoW) and Proof of Stake (PoS). In **PoW**, network nodes (miners) compete for the right to add a new block to the chain. This is determined by how quickly each element solves a cryptographic problem. The **PoS** mechanism works according to the principle of betting a certain number of coins on the network and selecting validators on this basis. PoS is characterized by lower energy consumption and higher operational efficiency [5].

Cryptography is an important component of data protection in the blockchain. Sophisticated algorithms are used to encrypt each transaction and block. This ensures that only authorized users can access the information. With this method of protection, hashing is used - the generation of a separate digital fingerprint.

Another unique aspect of the blockchain is the use of **smart contracts**. These software algorithms fulfill the terms of agreements between the parties without the use of intermediaries, which reduces the likelihood of fraud. Smart contracts allow you to automate various tasks, for example, financial transactions, digital asset management and verification of contract terms [6]. They offer a high level of trust and security, which makes them in demand in various industries such as financial services, logistics, real estate management and public administration.

Examples of successful use of blockchain in the IT infrastructure

American companies are actively using BT to optimize and protect their IT infrastructure. This provides them with a competitive advantage and increases data security. IBM is a leader in this field. He develops

blockchain solutions for supply chain management. IBM's Hyperledger Fabric-based blockchain platform is used, for example, in the IBM Food Trust project. It allows you to track food products at all stages of the supply chain – from the manufacturer to the end consumer. According to reports, the productivity of developers using Hyperledger Fabric has increased by 18%. At the same time, the cost of operations has decreased by 30% over three years of use, and unplanned downtime is eliminated 44% faster [7].

Walmart uses blockchain to monitor the quality and origin of products in its supply chain. In collaboration with IBM, the company has integrated the IBM Food Trust product tracking solution, which allows you to instantly check the history of products at all stages, from production to delivery to the store. This helps Walmart respond quickly to various incidents, such as the appearance of substandard goods, and eliminate possible disruptions in the supply chain.

Another example of successful use of blockchain is **Microsoft**. The company has implemented the Azure blockchain platform to integrate blockchain solutions using smart contracts. Azure supports both private and public blockchain networks. This provides customers with the opportunity to automate and improve processes.

JP Morgan, a large financial company, has made a significant step in the development of BT with the help of its Onyx platform. In 2023, up to \$2 billion in transactions were processed daily using this technology. This contributed to an increase in JP Morgan's operational efficiency and cost reduction, which had a positive impact on the company's profitability (pic. 4).

Pic. 4. Total net revenue of JP Morgan, million dollars [8]

One of the key products of the Onyx platform is JPM Coin, a digital currency backed by a bank that allows instant settlements between institutional clients. Onyx has also developed a blockchain-based Link network to optimize cross-border payments and improve information exchange between participating banks. These initiatives highlight JP Morgan's commitment to integrate cutting-edge technology into its financial ecosystem, making it a leader in blockchain adoption in the banking industry.

Features of using BT in IT infrastructure management

Blockchain have become increasingly popular in recent years and are widely used in IT infrastructure management, offering diverse and innovative opportunities to significantly increase the level of security, ensure transparency of all processes and increase the stability and reliability of systems. However, the implementation and integration of this complex mechanism faces many challenges and difficulties that require careful analysis and elaboration in order to effectively solve them (table 1).

Table 1

Features of implementing BT [9]		
Problem	Description	Solution
High implementation costs	Implementing blockchain requires significant financial and technical resources for adapting existing infrastructure and training personnel.	Piloting projects are recommended to assess the effectiveness and optimize costs; the use of ready-made infrastructure platforms can reduce setup and training expenses.
Integration complexity	Existing IT systems may be incompatible with blockchain platforms, complicating their integration and data synchronization.	The use of hybrid blockchain solutions, which allow existing systems to interact, and the development of APIs for data exchange between platforms.
Low scalability	Some blockchain platforms, especially public ones, face scalability issues that limit their performance and effectiveness for large data volumes.	The use of private or semi-private platforms and the choice of consensus algorithms (e.g., Proof of Stake) that provide higher transaction speeds.
Lack of qualified specialists	Implementing blockchain requires specialists with technical expertise and blockchain knowledge, which can become a challenge for many organizations.	Investment in education and training: offering courses for employees, attracting experienced consultants, and collaborating with companies specializing in blockchain technology.
Regulatory and legal barriers	There is a lack of clear regulatory frameworks for BT, which creates uncertainty for organizations, especially in areas related to data confidentiality.	Participation in blockchain standardization initiatives and collaboration with regulatory bodies to establish transparent legal frameworks for ensuring data confidentiality and compliance.
Complexity of management and updates	The decentralized nature of blockchain networks can complicate configuration management and software updates.	The use of smart contracts, which help automate certain management processes, and detailed documentation can reduce the risk of errors during configuration and updates.

The implementation of BT in the management of IT infrastructure requires an integrated approach and strategic planning. Developers must take into account technical, organizational, legal and economic aspects. To do this, it is necessary to develop comprehensive strategies with the involvement of relevant experts. Infrastructure adaptation and staff training can contribute to the successful development of projects, establish interaction with regulators and partners. This will minimize potential risks and costs, and maximize the benefits of new technologies.

Prospects for blockchain application in future IT infrastructures

The development of artificial intelligence (AI) and other new technologies, such as the Internet of Things (IoT), is affecting the blockchain. As noted above, the decentralized and transparent architecture of this technology allows for the security of complex projects. This is also used in AI systems. Thus, AI mechanisms often require training based on significant amounts of data. In this case, special attention to cybersecurity is required. Blockchain allows reliable and transparent data management, ensuring their integrity and protection from unauthorized access [10]. In addition, decentralized data storage in blockchain networks helps to minimize the risks associated with «points of failure». This is important for systems such as autonomous vehicles or medical devices.

The integration of blockchain with IoT also opens up new possibilities. Modern IoT devices generate a huge amount of data. There is a need to ensure their safety and proper use. The blockchain can be used to authenticate devices and encrypt data. This will help to ensure their protection at all stages of processing. For example, in smart cities, blockchain can become the basis for managing energy, transport systems and other resources.

Thus, the prospects for using blockchain in future IT infrastructures look promising. In combination with AI and IoT, blockchain can become part of new technological ecosystems. This will provide the transparency, security and adaptability needed to create sustainable and high-performance digital solutions.

Conclusion

The use of BT in IT infrastructure project management opens up new horizons in data security and process management. The decentralized structure of the blockchain and its immutability help to minimize the risks associated with cyber-attacks and data leaks. This is because each member of the network has access to the current version of the information and participates in the confirmation of changes. This increases the resilience of the infrastructure to internal and external threats. In addition, the blockchain ensures transpar-

ency of all transactions. This is important for monitoring and auditing IT systems. The integration of smart contracts automates access and update management, which reduces the likelihood of human error and increases data processing efficiency. As a result, blockchain enhances both security and transparency, but also contributes to the creation of more sustainable and flexible IT ecosystems that are able to adaptive IT ecosystems capable of meeting modern cybersecurity challenges and business needs.

References

1. Leiba M., Dahan E., Barger A., Bertha A., Aspir T. Addressing Infrastructure Requirements of Blockchain-Native Information System. 2024 IEEE 32nd International Requirements Engineering Conference Workshops (REW). IEEE, 2024. P. 330-339.
2. Vaigandla K. K., Siluveru M., Kesoju M., Kame R. Review on blockchain technology: architecture, characteristics, benefits, algorithms, challenges and applications//Mesopotamian Journal of CyberSecurity. 2023. V. 2023. P. 73-84.
3. Worldwide spending on blockchain solutions from 2017 to 2020, with forecasts for 2021 and 2024. Statista. URL: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/800426/worldwide-blockchain-solutions-spending/> (date of application: 15.10.2024)
4. Breaking blockchain open. Deloitte's 2018 global blockchain survey. URL: <https://www2.deloitte.com/content/dam/Deloitte/us/Documents/financial-services/usfsi-2018-global-blockchain-survey-report.pdf> (date of application: 17.10.2024)
5. Xu J., Wang C., Jia X. A survey of blockchain consensus protocols//ACM Computing Surveys. 2023. V. 55. №. 13s. P. 1-35.
6. Sidorov D. Asynchronous programming techniques and their impact on user experience in modern web applications. Znanstvena misel journal. 2024. № 94. P. 62-65.
7. IBM Support for Hyperledger Fabric. IBM. URL: <https://www.ibm.com/products/blockchain-platform-hyperledger-fabric> (date of application: 18.10.2024)
8. JP Morgan Annual Report 2023. JP Morgan. URL: <https://www.jpmorganchase.com/content/dam/jpmc/jpmorgan-chase-and-co/investor-relations/documents/annualreport-2023.pdf> (date of application: 19.10.2024)
9. Aluev A. Addressing security issues in node.js applications: the economic implications of increased security. International Journal of Humanities and Natural Sciences. 2024. V. 9-1(96). P. 94-98.
10. Verner D. Methods of backend system optimization for performance enhancement. Sciences of Europe. 2024. № 151. P. 110-112.